

Journal of Pure and Applied
Ultrasonics

Website : www.ultrasonicsindia.org

A Publication of Ultrasonics Society of India

An ultrasonic exploration of physico-chemical properties for mixtures of dichloroacetyl chloride with polar, non-polar and polymers at 300 K

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The present study is oriented towards the demonstration of physico-chemical properties and molecular interactions of the prepared binary mixture of Dichloroacetyl chloride (DCAC) with methanol/ethanol/CCl₄/PEGs through ultrasonic non-destructive characterization. The intermolecular interaction, structural ordering, and corrosiveness aspects of prepared binary mixtures have been interpreted on the basis of measured (density, viscosity, ultrasonic velocity) and estimated thermo-physical quantities (compressibility, free length, free volume, Gibb's free energy, thermal relaxation time, and ultrasonic absorption) at 300K. All binary mixtures have been received to undergo exothermic reaction during preparation while mixture DCAC + methanol has been found to produce excessive heat and harmful odour vapour. The study confirms that DCAC+CCl₄ consist of least intermolecular interaction while mixture DCAC with PEG600 possesses strong molecular interaction among constituents accomplished by intense hydrogen bonding and physical forces. It also concludes that DCAC + PEG600 shall be highly viscous and least corrosive in comparison to other prepared mixtures. The present study provides new dimension for applicability of hazardous chemical DCAC in mixture form toward herbicides, pesticides, and fertilizers industries.

Keywords: Binary liquid mixture, intermolecular interaction, physico-chemical properties, ultrasonic parameters.

Introduction

To understand the nature and strength of molecular interactions among the molecules of liquid mixtures, physico-chemical properties of liquid are very advantageous. These properties of mixtures are very helpful to design environmental friendly chemical products and minimizing the hazardousness of materials in the chemical and pharmaceutical industries¹⁻³. Study of volumetric, thermodynamic and viscometric properties of multi-component liquid mixtures provides foundation for chemical synthesis for industrial applications. In the field of chemicals and pharmaceuticals binary liquid mixtures have been found enormous applications. Ultrasonic characterization provides underlying information about the molecular

interaction of liquids and solids, due to its ability to characterize the physico-chemical behaviour of the medium^{4,5}. Thermo-physical properties of mixtures also provide valuable information about solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions⁶⁻⁸. Differences in molecular size, molar mass, temperature, pressure and mole fraction of constituent liquids in binary mixtures is the cause of non-linear deviations in density, viscosity and velocity, with ideal values for them. The variation in thermo-physical parameters and their additional values with structure provides an insight into the molecular process by investigating molecular interactions⁹⁻¹².

Dichloroacetyl chloride (DCAC) is an acyl chloride that is obtained through the displacement of the hydroxyl group of dichloroacetic acid by chloride. It is a polar and colorless liquid having pungent odor vapors that are irritating to eyes with mucous membranes and

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belongs to the corrosive, flammable, and reactive hazard class. It has a role as a haptene (a compound which, when coupled with a protein or other molecules, can cause the formation of antibodies) and it is also the precursor to antibiotics, including chloramphenicol^{13,14}. It is used not only in the manufacturing of fertilizers, pesticides, agrochemicals but also in preventing, destroying, and instigating pests.

Alcohols ($C_nH_{2n+1}OH$) are the organic polar compound that carries at least one ($-OH$) bound to saturated carbon atoms which are used as drugs. Methanol and ethanol are the simplest members of the alcohol family. The chemical and thermo-physical properties of Methanol/ethanol with nitriles, pyridine, dodecane, dimethylformamide, tetrahydrofuran, trichloromethane, ethyl acetate, methyl acetate, N, N-dimethylformamide, nitrobenzene, triethylamine has been reported in the literature¹⁵⁻²⁵.

Carbon tetrachloride (CCl_4) possesses non-polar, colorless, highly toxic, and non-flammable nature with intense odor characteristics. It belongs to the group of organic halogen compounds which is useful as fire sedative, refrigeration fluid, propellant etc. It is water-insoluble whereas compoundable with ethyl alcohol, ether, benzene, chloroform, and most other organic solvents. Intermolecular interaction studies on the basis of density, viscosity and ultrasonic velocity for liquid mixtures of CCl_4 with various chemicals have been reported elsewhere²⁶⁻³².

PEG have wide application in the field of food, pharmaceutical, cosmetic (skin cream), chemical industries, etc. due to environmental friendly nature with low toxicity, water solubility and excellent biocompatibility^{33,34}. Polyethylene glycols of different molecular weight as 200,400 and 600 are also known as PEG200, PEG400, and PEG600, respectively. Due to having $-O-$ and $-OH$ groups in the identical molecule, PEG consists of good proton donor and acceptor ability. This feature makes it compatible to form inter- and intra-molecular hydrogen bonding with other molecules². Due to excellent properties, PEG can also be used in the fuel gas desulfurization. The thermo-physical study of PEG200/400/600 with dimethyl sulfoxide, tetrabutylammonium bromide, o-cresol, benzene and toluene, 2 butanol, cyclic ether, water and ethanol, ionic liquid, ionic liquid BMIBF₄, water, ethanolamine, m-Cresol and aniline have been narrated in the literature using ultrasonic technique³³⁻⁴⁶.

No work has been done for binary mixture of Dichloroacetyl chloride with methanol/ethanol/ CCl_4 /PEGs in the literature using ultrasonic non-destructive testing whereas they have a significant role in the field of chemical industries. Hence, the present study is concentrated on ultrasonic characterization of binary mixtures containing DCAC and methanol/ethanol/ CCl_4 /PEGs at 300K and 100.5 kPa to find out physico-chemical characteristic related to molecular interaction. On the basis of ultrasonic and related thermo-physical parameters, molecular interaction and characteristic features of prepared binary mixtures have been explored at 300K.

Synthesis

The chemical Dichloroacetyl chloride has been considered as solute to make the binary mixture. The DCAC and Polymer (PEGs) has 98% purity and has been manufactured by Sigma Aldrich Chemical Pvt. Ltd. Bangalore India and Thomas Baker Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, India respectively whereas the chemicals methanol/ethanol, carbon tetrachloride (CCl_4), and PEG200/400/600 have been taken as polar, non-polar and polymer solvents, respectively for the preparation of the binary mixture. The methanol and ethanol contain 99.5% and 99.9% purity, respectively and have been manufactured by Sigma Aldrich Chemical Pvt. Ltd. Bangalore India while CCl_4 have 99% purity and have been manufactured by Molychem Chemicals Pvt. Ltd. Mumbai, India. The basic specifications of the chemicals used in the study are listed in Table 1, while their chemical structures are depicted in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of the studied Compound

The binary mixtures have been prepared by taking the solute and solvents in volume by volume ratio 47. The Dichloroacetyl chloride (20%, 6 mL) and methanol/ethanol/ CCl_4 /PEGs (80%, 24 mL) have been taken as

Table 1 – Details of Used Chemicals (Chemicals/formula, CAS number, Molar mass, Source, Mass fraction purity, Water content and Analysis method).

Chemicals/formula	CAS Number	Molar mass (g.mol ⁻¹)	Source	Mass fraction purity (%)	Water content (Mass %)	Analysis method
Dichloroacetyl chloride (CHCl ₂ COCl)	79-36-7	147.38	Sigma Aldrich Chem. Pvt.Ltd. Bangalore, India	98	Not detected	KF [#]
Methanol (CH ₃ OH)	67-56-1	32.04	Sigma Aldrich Chem. Pvt.Ltd. Bangalore, India	99.5	0.02	GC [*]
Ethanol (C ₂ H ₅ OH)	64-17-5	46.07	Sigma Aldrich Chem. Pvt.Ltd. Bangalore,India	99.9	0.02	GC [*]
Carbon tetrachloride (CCl ₄)	56-23-5	153.82	Molychem Chem. Pvt. Ltd Mumbai, India	99	0.02	GC [*]
PEG200 (H(OCH ₂ CH ₂) _n OH)	25322-68-3	200	Thomas Baker (Chem.) Pvt. Ltd. Mumbai, India	98	0.30 ± 0.02	KF [#]
PEG400 (H(OCH ₂ CH ₂) _n OH)	25322-68-3	400	Thomas Baker (Chem.) Pvt. Ltd. Mumbai, India	98	0.36 ± 0.02	KF [#]
PEG600 (H(OCH ₂ CH ₂) _n OH)	25322-68-3	600	Thomas Baker (Chem.) Pvt. Ltd. Mumbai, India	98	0.46 ± 0.02	KF [#]

* Professed by supplier, #Karl Fischer titration method.

constituents to form six samples from 30 mL of binary mixture. All the binary mixtures, during preparation, have been found to be highly exothermic. The highest exothermic nature is observed for the mixture of DCAC with polar solvent methanol. Since chemical DCAC evaporates noxious odour vapours which are harmful and hazardous to the eyes with mucous membranes and also it's very low amount produces a high exothermic reaction, therefore the low percentage of it has been taken to make the binary mixture.

The water content in Dichloroacetyl chloride and PEGs was determined by Karl Fischer titration method (Model no. KAFI-KF12240121, LABINDIA). In the process of titration, mixture of SO₂, I₂ and pyridine have been used as KF reagent while dry methanol as solvent. The water content in constituent liquids is presented in Table 1. Purchased chemicals have not undergone any purification prior to preparation of binary mixtures. All the samples have been prepared at 300K and 1atm. The measurement of pressure has been done

Table 2 – Mole fraction of constituents in binary samples of Dichloroacetyl chloride with methanol/ethanol/CCl₄/PEGs at 300K and atmospheric pressure (100.5kPa).

Samples	Abbreviation ↓	Components ↓	Mole Fraction
Dichloroacetyl chloride + Methanol	S ₁	DCAC	0.0961
		Methanol	0.9039
Dichloroacetyl chloride + Ethanol	S ₂	DCAC	0.1337
		Ethanol	0.8663
Dichloroacetyl chloride + CCl ₄	S ₃	DCAC	0.2038
		CCl ₄	0.7962
Dichloroacetyl chloride + PEG200	S ₄	DCAC	0.3269
		PEG 200	0.6731
Dichloroacetyl chloride + PEG400	S ₅	DCAC	0.4907
		PEG 400	0.5093
Dichloroacetyl chloride + PEG600	S ₆	DCAC	0.5890
		PEG 600	0.4110

by digital Barometer and found to be 100.5 kPa. The uncertainty was found in pressure measurement in present study is ± 0.15 kPa. The mole fraction of constituents in prepared mixtures is listed in Table 2.

Experimental

Density Measurement

The densities of binary liquid mixtures were determined using the density bottle method at 300K and atmospheric pressure 100.5 kPa. For this, density bottle (25 mL) with tolerance capacity ± 0.8 mL and digital electronic balance having accuracy $\pm 1 \times 10^{-3}$ g have been used. The density bottle is calibrated by distilled water (0.9965 g.cm^{-3})^{2,5}. The uncertainty in density (ρ) and temperature measurements are $\pm 1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ g.cm}^{-3}$ and $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ respectively.

Viscosity Measurements

The determination of viscosity (η) of prepared mixtures has been performed by Poiseuille method^{2,49,50}. The measurement was completed by observing the outflow time of fixed volume of samples with capillary thin tube using digital stopwatch (accuracy-0.01s). Distill water (viscosity-0.8502 mPa.s) was used as reference fluid in estimation of mixture viscosity^{2,5}. The sample temperature was maintained by water bath thermostat (accuracy- $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$). The uncertainty in measured viscosity is $\pm 2.1\%$.

Ultrasonic velocity Measurements

The ultrasonic interferometer has been used to measure the ultrasonic velocity (U) of the liquid mixtures. The credibility of measurements have been checked by receiving sound velocity data for distill water at 300K^{4,5}. The present sound velocity in distill water at 300K has been observed $1502.5 \pm 0.6 \text{ m.s}^{-1}$ while the reported values of it at 298K and 301K are $1496.65 \pm 0.1 \text{ m.s}^{-1}$ and $1504.29 \pm 0.1 \text{ m.s}^{-1}$, respectively^{2,51}. The uncertainty in present velocity measurements is $\pm 0.6 \text{ m.s}^{-1}$.

Theoretical Aspects

Thermo-physical Parameters

Isentropic/adiabatic Compressibility

Intermolecular association and orientation of the solvent molecules around the solute molecules can be described on the basis of isentropic compressibility.

The compressibility of the binary mixtures can be determined using the following expression^{1-3,5}.

$$\beta = \frac{1}{U^2 \rho} \quad (1)$$

Intermolecular Free Length

Determination of free length in liquids and liquid mixtures has been subject to a semi-empirical relation to obtaining the intermolecular free length. The free length is the separation between the surfaces of adjacent molecules of the binary mixture. The free length can be determined by following Jacobson relation¹⁻².

$$L_f = K_T \beta^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

where, K_T is the constant and its value is 198×10^8 .

Free volume

Free volume (V_f) is defined as the average volume in which the center of the molecules can move inside the hypothetical cell due to the repulsion of the surrounding molecules. The determination of the free volume of a binary mixture can be determined using viscosity (η), ultrasonic velocity (U) and effective molar mass (M_{eff}) of that mixture^{2,4}.

$$V_f = \left(\frac{M_{eff} U}{\eta K} \right)^{3/2} \quad (3)$$

where, constant K has value is 4.28×10^9 .

Thermal Relaxation Time

The relaxation time (τ) is the time in which the structural deformation by propagation of ultrasonic wave is restored in the medium through translational motion. It depends on the temperature and impurities and can be evaluated using the following relation¹⁻⁵.

$$\tau = \frac{4}{3} \beta \eta \quad (4)$$

Gibb's Free Energy

The energy involved in the formation of binary mixture with constituents through structural relaxation process is measured by Gibb's free energy. The Eyring-salt process theory provides following expression for the Gibb's free energy and thermal relaxation time¹⁻².

$$\Delta G = -KT \log \left(\frac{h}{KT\tau} \right) \quad (5)$$

Ultrasonic Absorption

The loss of energy of ultrasonic waves by the concerned medium is called ultrasonic attenuation. The ultrasonic absorption/attenuation over frequency square

(αf^2) in a binary mixture can be calculated theoretically using the following expression¹⁻⁵.

$$\left(\frac{\alpha}{f^2}\right) = \frac{8\pi^2\eta}{3\rho U^3} \quad (6)$$

Results and Discussion

The measured density, viscosity and ultrasonic velocity for pure liquids (Dichloroacetyl chloride, methanol/ethanol/CCl₄/PEGs) are shown in Table 3 and are found very close to reported values given in the literature^{20,21,29,30,32,41,43,44}. Therefore, our measured quantities are justified. The same measured quantities for binary mixtures of DCAC with methanol/ethanol/CCl₄/PEGs are given in Table 4 and presented in Figs. 2-3. The acoustical and thermo-physical parameters of the prepared binary samples are estimated through measured quantities and Eqs.1-6 which are presented in Table 5 and depicted in Figs. 3-6.

The measured density has been observed to decay slowly for polar-polar mixtures (S₁ to S₂) with an increase in molar mass while it increases very rapidly

for polar + non-polar mixture (S₃), and finally, it decreases and saturates with molar mass for polar + polymer mixtures (S₄ to S₆) [Fig. 2]. The decrease in density from mixture S₁ to S₂ indicates that accommodation of solute molecules between the intermolecular spacing of solvent decays with enhancement in the molar mass of polar solvent. An intense increase in density for the polar + non-polar mixture (S₃) confirms that accommodation of DCAC within non-polar solvent shall be high. The density for polar + polymer mixtures (S₄ to S₆) is found to be in between the densities of polar + polar and polar + non-polar binary liquid mixtures under study. This reveals that the compactness of molecules for polar + polymer mixtures shall lie in between both other types of mixtures formed with DCAC. The density of polar + polymer mixture (DCAC+PEG200/400/600) is observed to enhance slowly with molar mass, which indicates that the bonding between constituent liquids enhances with molar mass of polymer solvent. The variation of density with a molar mass of all three types of mixtures has been found to follow a non-linear curve.

Table 3 – Density, viscosity and ultrasonic velocity for constituents of prepared binary mixtures at fixed mole fraction of each solute/solvent.

Components ↓	T (K)	Density (10 ³ kg m ⁻³)		Viscosity (mPa.s)		Velocity (m s ⁻¹)	
		Present	Lit.	Present	Lit.	Present	Lit.
Dichloroacetyl chloride	300	1.532	1.532 (at 298K)	1.266	-	934	-
Methanol	298	-	0.7863 ²⁰	-	0.551 ²⁰	-	1108 ²⁰
	300	0.783	-	0.531	-	1086	-
	303	-	0.7824 ²¹	-	0.508 ²¹	-	1088 ²¹
Ethanol	298	-	0.7843 ²⁰	-	1.084 ²⁰	-	1144 ²⁰
	300	0.776	-	1.054	-	1132	-
	303	-	0.7812 ²¹	-	0.987 ²¹	-	1128 ²¹
CCl ₄	298	-	1.584 ²⁹	-	0.821 ²⁹	-	0.918 ²⁹
	300	1.562	-	0.879	-	916	-
	303	-	1.559 ³²	-	0.768 ³⁰	-	0.906 ³²
PEG200	298	-	1.0086 ⁴³	-	-	-	1535.5 ⁴³
	300	1.070	-	40.249	-	1540.0	-
	303	-	1.116 ⁴⁴	-	38.72 ⁴¹	-	1567.7 ⁴⁴
PEG400	298	-	1.0191 ⁴³	-	-	-	1572.5 ⁴³
	300	1.079	-	71.224	-	1576.3	-
	303	-	-	-	69.62 ⁴¹	-	-
PEG600	298	-	1.0289 ⁴³	-	-	-	1605.7 ⁴³
	300	1.088	-	96.344	-	1607.0	-
	303	-	-	-	101.7 ⁴¹	-	-

Viscosity is received to resemble the opposite nature of the molar mass-dependent density of three types of samples. It is clear from Table 4 and Fig. 2, that the viscous/internal frictional force will be large for the binary mixtures DCAC with PEGs while it will be least for mixture of DCAC with methanol. The viscosity characteristic also informs that the shear stress and lateral forces among molecules will be high for mixture of polar DCAC and polymer PEGs. The enhancement in viscosity with molar mass for polar + polymer mixture (Fig. 2) is caused by strengthening of lateral bonding between constituents. The low viscosity for polar + non-polar mixture (DCAC + CCl₄) in comparison to the polar-polymer mixture confirms the presence of weak shear forces. The viscosity of the polar + polar mixture is found very close to the viscosity of the polar + non-polar mixture.

The velocity of ultrasonic wave has been found lowest for mixture S₃ (DCAC + CCl₄) while a continuous enhancement in it for the polar-polar and polar-polymer mixtures (S₁ to S₂ and S₄ to S₆) has been obtained (Table 4 and Fig. 3). The ultrasonic velocity is directly

proportional to the square root of the bulk modulus. The quantity bulk modulus measures the amount of internal stress/force per unit strain. Therefore, ultrasonic velocity provides a direct consequence of the strength of bonding among the molecules. The lowest velocity for the mixture of DCAC + CCl₄ confirms the existence of the weak intermolecular interaction. Hence, the strength of physical forces acting among molecules of DCAC + CCl₄ mixture shall be feeble. The comparatively high ultrasonic velocity for polar-polar mixture explores the existence of relatively strong bonding among the constituents. An increase in the ultrasonic velocity of polar + polymer mixtures (S₄ to S₆) confirms the presence of strong bonding network between DCAC and PEG. The bonding network shall be more strengthen and directional for the mixture of DCAC with PEG600 as velocity for it is observed high.

The compressibility is found to decrease continuously in polar + polar, polar + non-polar, and polar + polymers with the molar mass of mixture (Table 5). This indicates that the mixture of DCAC with PEG600 shall be least compressible. The free length defines the average space

Fig. 2. Density and Viscosity vs. Molar mass of binary mixtures at 300K

Fig. 3. Ultrasonic Velocity and Compressibility vs. Molar mass of binary mixtures at 300K.

Table 4 – Measured quantities of binary mixture of DCAC with methanol/ethanol/CCl₄/PEGs at 300K.

Binary Samples →	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅	S ₅
Properties ↓						
Molar Mass (g.mol ⁻¹)	43.126	59.611	152.508	182.797	276.046	333.405
Density (10 ³ kg m ⁻³)	0.938	0.931	1.554	1.137	1.146	1.156
Viscosity (mPa.s)	0.634	1.160	0.958	29.100	39.007	42.408
Ultrasonic velocity (m s ⁻¹)	1150.4	1202.2	957.6	1591.5	1634.8	1671.2

Table 5 – Calculated value of compressibility (β), free length (L_f), free volume (V_f), thermal relaxation time (τ), Gibb's free energy (ΔG), and ultrasonic absorption (α/f^2) of DCAC and methanol/ethanol/ CCl_4 /PEGs at 300K and atmospheric pressure (100.5 kPa).

Samples ↓	Molar Mass	β $10^{-10}\text{N}^{-1}\text{m}^2$	L_f 10^{-10}m	V_f $10^{-10}\text{m}^3\text{mol}^{-1}$	τ 10^{-12}s	ΔG $10^{-21}\text{J}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$	α/f^2 $10^{-17}\text{Np}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}\text{cm}^{-1}$
S_1	43.126	8.057	5.620	781.780	0.681	2.606	11.675
S_2	59.611	7.435	5.398	548.410	1.149	3.548	18.862
S_3	152.508	7.017	5.245	2125.700	0.896	3.100	18.458
S_4	182.797	3.472	3.689	35.700	13.470	7.975	166.900
S_5	276.046	3.263	3.577	44.442	16.975	8.391	204.760
S_6	333.405	3.098	3.485	53.407	17.602	8.456	207.700

Standard uncertainties $u(M_w) = \pm 5.1\%$, $u(\beta) = \pm 0.001 \times 10^{-10} \text{N}^{-1} \text{m}^2$, $u(L_f) = \pm 0.001 \times 10^{-10} \text{m}$,

$u(V_f) = \pm 0.001 \times 10^{-10} \text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$, $u(\tau) = \pm 0.001 \times 10^{-12} \text{s}$, $u(\Delta G) = \pm 0.001 \times 10^{-21} \text{joule mol}^{-1}$ and $u(\alpha/f^2) = \pm 0.001 \times 10^{-17} \text{Np}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}\text{cm}^{-1}$

among atoms (atomic separation) and is well correlated with compressibility. The significant interaction among constituent molecules of binary mixture enhances the compactness between solute and solvent and settles low atomic separation and compressibility. Therefore, the trends of molar mass dependent free length and compressibility have been found same for present mixtures (Figs. 3-4).

The free volume of polar + polar mixture (S_1 to S_2) is found to decrease with an increase in the molar mass of solvent (Fig. 4) while for polar + non-polar mixture (S_3) it rapidly increases in comparison to polar + polar mixture and hereinafter it is observe to decrease for polymers and tends to saturate with enhancement in molar mass. Decay in free volume for S_1 to S_2 indicates, the accommodation of solute molecules between the

intermolecular free space of solvent has been decaying. For polar + non-polar mixture (S_3), an acute enhancement in free volume is seen which confirms that accommodation of solute within non-polar solvent shall be high. Similar result has been reported in the literature for mixture of toluene + CCl_4 ¹⁷. Comparatively, the low free volume has been obtained for the present polar-polymer mixture (S_4 to S_6) that increases slightly with molar mass. The overall variation of free volume with molar mass of mixtures is found to follow the characteristic of density.

The thermal relaxation time and Gibb's free energy are observed to increase with solvent molar mass in polar + polar mixture (S_1 to S_2) and polar + polymers (S_4 , S_5 and S_6) which is shown in Fig. 5. But for polar + non-polar mixture (S_3), both the parameters received to

Fig. 4. Free Length and Free volume vs. Molar mass of binary mixtures at 300K.

Fig. 5. Gibb's free energy and Th. Relaxation time vs. Molar mass of binary mixtures at 300K.

decrease slowly with increase in molar mass of mixture. The thermal relaxation time is well correlated with viscosity and compressibility of liquid. The compressibility is received to decay with the molar mass while viscosity is received to enhance in the polar + polar mixture and polar + polymer mixture. But for polar + non-polar mixture, the viscosity is somewhat low. Therefore, both of these parameters together affect molar mass dependent thermal relaxation time in polar + polar, polar + non-polar and polar + polymer mixtures. The structural relaxation process for rearrangement of molecules in present mixture with hydrogen bonding and dipole interaction through accommodating process is confirmed by pico-second order of thermal relaxation time^{52,53}. Gibb's free energy of mixture defines the maximum work done in formation of it with constituents in equilibrium condition through relaxation process. Therefore, Gibb's free energy and thermal relaxation time resemble the same trend of variation with molar mass for present mixtures.

The nature of ultrasonic absorption is received to resemble characteristics of molar mass-dependent thermal relation time and Gibb's free energy (Fig. 6). The viscosity has been obtained to be the governing factor for ultrasonic absorption in the present binary liquid mixtures. An enhancement in ultrasonic absorption reveals a high ordering and significant bonding among the constituents due to exceptional hydration and the presence of physical forces through a vibrational relaxation mechanism. The analysis of ultrasonic absorption signifies that the ordering and

Fig. 6. Ultrasonic absorption vs. Molar mass of binary mixtures at 300K.

bonding among the constituents shall be high for DCAC +PEG600 mixture due to presence of strong physical forces evinced by huge hydrogen bonding and network formation.

Conclusion

The analysis reveals that measured and estimated thermo-physical quantities for binary liquid mixtures of Dichloroacetyl chloride (DCAC) with methanol/ethanol/carbon tetrachloride and polyethylene glycol at 300K and 100.5 kPa are justified. The deep investigation of measured and estimated parameters confirms the presence of weak intermolecular physical forces between the constituents in the present binary mixtures. The ultrasonic and related thermo-physical parameters explores that DCAC shall form a stable and strengthen binary mixture with polymers in comparison to mixture with polar and non-polar liquids. It also explores that DCAC+PEG600 mixture have significant ordering and strong bonding among the constituents in comparison to other prepared mixtures due to huge hydrogen bonding and network formation. This reveals that DCAC + PEG600 shall have low corrosiveness and high stability. The present work shall open a new dimension for the further study of hazardous chemical DCAC and shall also enhance its applicability in the form of a low corrosive binary mixture in the field of herbicides, pesticides, and fertilizers.

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